

Interfacial Straining Mechanisms Enabling Ultra-Sensitive Molecular Detection at Microfluidic Liquid Crystal Interfaces

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ABSTRACT

Detecting aqueous trace pollutants is a challenge in tracking environmental and public health. We report nanoparticle-decorated liquid crystal (LC) soft interfaced microfluidic platforms for detecting trace-level aqueous analytes. Silica nanoparticles functionalized with alkyl-terminated silanes were used to decorate the LC–aqueous interfaces and induce LC strain. The response of the LC flow sensor to various analytes, including industrial dyes, pharmaceuticals, and persistent chemicals, was investigated through the optically observable LC ordering transitions. The microfluidic results, supported by nanoparticle-integrated LC droplet-based sensors, showed a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.1 ppb with LC-interfaces decorated with concentrated nanoparticles. Lowering the interfacial nanoparticle loading resulted in sensors achieving an impressive four orders of magnitude reduction in the LOD. While LC droplet-based sensors were unable to reach this sensitivity limit, such ultralow responses were strikingly observed in microfluidic sensor platforms by leveraging the interface geometry and localized straining at LC interfaces induced by nanoparticle positioning. We show that the sensors demonstrate selectivity for analytes characterized by aromatic structures. These features hold potential for various applications, including continuous tracking of micropollutants and medical diagnostics.

KEYWORDS: liquid crystals, nanoparticles, microfluidics, ultra-sensitive sensors, aqueous pollutants

1. INTRODUCTION

The detection of trace-level concentrations of species in an aqueous medium (ng/L to $\mu\text{g/L}$ range) is of paramount importance due to global concerns regarding the unfavorable impacts of micropollutants on health and the ecosystem.¹⁻³ This raises an apparent demand for sensor platforms that can facilitate straightforward and continuous measurements while being tailorable and adaptable for a diverse range of chemical species. The comprehensive investigations into liquid crystals (LCs), specifically the nematic LC phase, have revealed their considerable potential for label-free sensing applications.⁴⁻⁶ The sensing mechanism in chemical- and biological sensors utilizing LCs as signal reporters relies on the existence of an interfacial stimuli, including electrostatic interaction, physical adsorption, or chemical binding, to perturb the interfacial orientational ordering of the LCs.^{7, 8} Such interfacial ordering transition of LCs transforms into optical signals owing to the long-range orientational ordering and inherent optical anisotropy of the LCs, allowing for easy visual rendering under a polarized optical microscope.⁹ Thus, they function as an “optical amplifier” of the interfacial interactions, responding to external stimuli through ordering transitions over a short time period.¹⁰⁻¹² Recent studies regarding LCs in responsive systems have primarily concentrated on their interfacial phenomena in aqueous media, namely their interactions with analytes in aqueous phase for sensing objectives, the synthesis of nanostructured materials, and their responses to chemical or mechanical stresses at the LCs interfaces.¹³⁻¹⁹ Despite promising reported results that could be leveraged for critical applications, the findings have predominantly been constrained to stagnant LC systems, which significantly limit their use in continuous operation contexts. However, the advancement of the encouraging achievements in stagnant LC systems can be realized through the integration of LCs into automated flow systems for pivotal applications, including point-of-care and marker-based diagnostics, early warning/prognosis evaluation of disease, environmental/public health monitoring, and real-time industrial control among others, which demand high-throughput, continuous, or periodic analysis and rapid action. These features can be unlocked when LC-based sensors meet microfluidics.

Microfluidics enables the accurate control and manipulation of fluids within microscale channels, facilitating the miniaturization of intricate laboratory processes such as detection, separation, and sample preparation into monolithic, portable systems.^{20, 21} Lab-on-a-chip systems constructed in

microfluidics have emerged as an effective tool in the development of sensing platforms, offering transformative advantages like simple integration, drastically reduced detection time, ultralow sample consumption, efficient mass transfer, and field-deployable portability.²² However, limitations in sensitivity and selectivity, such as low detectable signals and a poor signal-to-noise ratio, are ongoing challenges in microfluidic systems.²³⁻²⁶ The integration of microfluidics with advanced/soft functional materials, including nanomaterials^{25, 27-30} and LCs hold promise to address these restrictions and promote the performance of microfluidic sensors. Nanomaterials demonstrate distinctive properties, including tunable interfacial chemistry, high surface-to-volume ratio, and enhanced signal amplification, positioning them as attractive candidates for improving the sensor performance, including sensitivity and selectivity to detect trace-level concentrations.^{24, 31} We have recently demonstrated that the nanoparticle-assisted LC droplet-based sensors enable the detection of species that do not directly induce an ordering transition at the LC–water interfaces. This functionality expands the range of analytical targets that can be effectively analyzed.³²

Despite its potential, the recent investigations into LC microfluidics are limited in providing accessible, free LC–aqueous interfaces for the exchange of external species because of the presence of solid interfaces confining LCs. Following the research on the hard interface³³⁻³⁶ and droplet-based microfluidics,³⁷⁻³⁹ the significance of developing and customizing a stable, externally attainable “soft” interface between LC and aqueous phases has become increasingly prominent. The formation of stable soft LC–aqueous interfaces enable the monitoring of spatiotemporal changes in the ordering of LC phases owing to the subtle response of the LCs to the chemical and mechanical stimuli at their aqueous interfaces. Such a platform not only facilitates the integration of LCs into continuous systems but also paves the way for enhancing the capabilities of the LC-based responsive systems, including automated flow devices for advanced analytical techniques. Recently, we succeeded in stabilizing the aqueous interfaces and quantifying the structural transitions in flowing nematic LCs confined in microfluidic channels with accessible LC–aqueous soft interfaces.^{40, 41} However, developing such a platform to attain reliable high-throughput responsive systems that can be integrated with advanced materials for cutting-edge sensing purposes, including the detection of solutes in aqueous phases that do not readily cause a direct ordering transition at the LC–aqueous interface, has yet to be achieved.

In this study, we investigate the fabrication of nanoparticle-integrated LC-based microfluidic sensors within microchannels featuring stable soft interfaces between thermotropic nematic 4-cyano-4'-pentylbiphenyl (5CB, an anisotropic oil) and aqueous phases, to detect low-concentration analyte molecules from the aqueous phase. To this end, we decorated the LC–aqueous interface with concentrated, functional fluorescent silica nanoparticles and investigated the response characteristics of the nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensors against a range of industrially or environmentally relevant chemical species. We revealed how the structuring of the adsorbed nanoparticles at the LC–aqueous interface can dramatically affect the sensitivity, such that the LOD of the nanoparticle-concentrated interface was measured as low as 0.1 ppb, while diluted nanoparticle-interfaced counterparts exhibited a substantial decrease in the LOD by four orders of magnitude (ppt-level). We found that the significant enhancement in LOD was directly related to the positioning of the nanoparticles at the interfaces, forming local anchoring heterogeneities (thus straining) that cause a favorable anchoring transition at ppt concentration levels. We demonstrate that the functionalized nanoparticles exhibit favorable selectivity performance in the detection of various analytes, particularly those with aromatic structures. The developed sensor is expected to achieve widespread application in automated flow systems, including the tracking of trace pollutants in aqueous environments, while offering a path for future advancements in the field.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Within a microfluidic channel, a stable and well-defined soft “virtual wall” interface between 5CB (Figure 1a) and an aqueous phase was maintained, spanning 1.5 cm in length and 14 μm in depth. This was achieved by employing a selective surface functionalization strategy that leverages the wetting properties of the immiscible thermotropic room-temperature nematic LC (5CB) and aqueous phases. Specifically, one longitudinal side of the microchannel was rendered hydrophobic through a flow-focusing of an aqueous solution of DMOAP, while the remaining side was left uncoated to retain its hydrophilic nature.^{40, 41} This spatially patterned wettability enabled the preferential filling of the DMOAP-coated side of the channel with 5CB upon co-introduction with water at controlled inlet pressures, thereby generating a microfluidic system featuring a robust 5CB–water interface. The stability of the “virtual wall” separating the co-flowing 5CB and water was confirmed through brightfield and polarized light microscopy, as shown in Figure 1d. The flow of 5CB and aqueous phases during the experiments was all horizontal from the top-view (x-

y plane). The dark optical texture observed under polarized light indicated a uniform perpendicular alignment of the 5CB director field relative to the imaging plane, driven by the homeotropic anchoring at the DMOAP-functionalized interfaces and minimal flow-induced distortion of the LC director field. Additionally, the 5CB–water interface exhibited planar anchoring, consistent with the dark appearance observed in the polarized micrographs. The fluorescence micrographs appeared dark, as pure water was used in the aqueous phase. The LC director profile across the channel is depicted in the cross-sectional schematic in Figure 1f (top).

Figure 1b schematically illustrates the structure of fluorescent silica nanoparticles functionalized by DMOAP (henceforth referred to as DMOAP F-SiNPs). The scanning electron microscope (SEM) micrograph of DMOAP F-SiNPs presented in Figure 1c revealed that the synthesized nanoparticles exhibit spherical morphology, with an average particle size of around 70 ± 6 nm. The measured size was in significant agreement with the average hydrodynamic diameter of particles determined to be 72 ± 3 nm through dynamic light scattering (DLS) analysis (Figure 1c, inset). By introducing the aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension with $\text{pH} = 2$ to the system, the 5CB–aqueous phase interface was shifted to homeotropic anchoring upon the adsorption of nanoparticles to the interface. Polarized optical microscopy confirmed the anchoring transition, showing a bright appearance at the 5CB–aqueous interface after the microchannel treatment with the nanoparticle suspension (Figure 1e), as illustrated in the schematic configuration in Figure 1f (bottom). Such homeotropic anchoring of 5CB was also reflected as a dark halo above the interface in the brightfield image. The presence of DMOAP F-SiNPs and their decoration at the interface of 5CB and the aqueous phase was validated using fluorescence microscopy (Figure 1e).

Recently, it was demonstrated that the nanoparticle-assisted LC droplet sensors are promising in the determination of the aqueous soluble analytes that do not cause a direct ordering transition at the LC–water interfaces.³² While we were inspired by such work, our approach was distinct and more pragmatic. We first developed the nanoparticle-decorated LC–aqueous interface within the microfluidic platform, and subsequently introduced the analytical species to ascertain their concentrations in the aqueous medium. This differed from the typical method in the literature, which equilibrates nanoparticles and analytes before exposing them to the LC droplets interface. To achieve this, the 5CB–water interface was decorated with $\sim 10^9$ particles/mL of DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension, followed by the injection of a 10 ppb aqueous solution (as a demonstration) of

Methylene Blue (MB) (Figure 1a) into the channel. The experiment was conducted at low bulk and interfacial shear stress with equal 5CB and aqueous phase inlet pressures $P_{5CB} = P_{Aq.} = 5$ mbar, to avoid the free displacement of nanoparticles owing to the high shear stress and enable effective adsorption of dye molecules onto the nanoparticles. Under these conditions, we measured the interfacial velocity to be $<1 \mu\text{m/s}$, confirming their insignificant displacement. As is evident from the polarized light micrographs in Figure 1g, the bright appearance of the nanoparticle-decorated 5CB–aqueous interface assumed a darker appearance over time, indicating the transition of 5CB from a homeotropic to planar interfacial anchoring. The analyte sensing process was accomplished in 20 min for a 10 ppb concentration of MB. The brightfield micrographs also indicated that the dark halo at the interface faded over time due to this transition. The fluorescence micrographs revealed that the adsorbed nanoparticles at the interface did not show a significant displacement during the sensing process (bottom row of Figure 1g). Hence, the interfacial ordering transition of 5CB from homeotropic to planar anchoring was attributed to the adsorption of MB molecules to the nanoparticle-decorated 5CB–aqueous interface. Rinsing the channel with fresh water at the end of the “sensing process” demonstrated that the system was reversible (Figure 1h). This means that while the nanoparticles maintained their position at the interface, the adsorbed MB molecules can be desorbed from the nanoparticle-decorated 5CB interface and washed away with the water flow. Consequently, 5CB transitioned from a planar to a homeotropic interfacial orientation, resulting in the 5CB–water interface appearing bright under the polarized optical microscope, as illustrated in Figure 1h.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of (a) 5CB, MB and (b) DMOAP employed for functionalizing the F-SiNPs. (c) SEM micrograph of the F-SiNPs. The inset shows the corresponding hydrodynamic particle size measured by DLS. The polarized (P), brightfield (B), and fluorescence (F) microscopy images of (d) 5CB–water and (e) 5CB–aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs (pH = 2) systems in a channel during weak flow, representing the planar and homeotropic anchoring of 5CB–aqueous interface, respectively. (f) Schematic illustration of the cross-sectional nematic director configuration maintained in microfluidic channels featuring planar or homeotropic aqueous interfaces. (g) Response of the nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensor ($\sim 10^9$ particles/mL of DMOAP F-SiNPs) to 10 ppb MB concentration over time, showing the orientational ordering transition of the interface from homeotropic to planar anchoring upon adsorption of MB molecules to the interface in 20 min. (h) Rinsing the channel with water at the end of the sensing process reveals that the system is reversible, allowing the interface to change to the homeotropic state as the MB molecules are removed. Scale bars: 1 μm for the SEM micrograph; 100 μm for the P, B, and F micrographs and 10 μm for their zoomed parts.

A series of experiments was conducted to demonstrate that the homeotropic 5CB–aqueous interface state achieved in Figure 1e was specifically assigned to the effective appearance of the nanoparticles at the interface. As stated earlier, an aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension with pH = 2 was employed to decorate the 5CB–water interface with the nanoparticles. The application of

such an acidic pH was necessitated by the observation that using the nanoparticle suspension at its initial pH of 7 resulted in the rapid occlusion of the channel inlet on the aqueous side, which consequently led to the swift termination of the experimental procedures. This blockage occurred owing to the strong affinity of the positively charged DMOAP F-SiNPs to adsorb onto either the inherently negatively charged glass or the PDMS that was bonded to it through the oxygen plasma treatment, which imparted negative charges.^{42, 43} As a result, there was a significant aggregation of nanoparticles in the early stages of the aqueous inlet, where the concentration of nanoparticles was particularly high (Figure 2a). Injecting the nanoparticle suspension at a pH of 2 effectively eliminated the channel blockage. At this acidic pH, although the interfacial charge of the DMOAP F-SiNPs remained positive, the silanol groups on the glass and PDMS surfaces became protonated, and their negative surface charges were significantly reduced.^{42, 44} Hence, the electrostatic attraction between the nanoparticles and the channel glass-PDMS walls was mitigated, allowing the nanoparticles to move along the channel and decorate the interface. To investigate the effect of pH on the 5CB–aqueous interface, we introduced water with pH = 2 to a microchannel. As shown in Figure 2b, such acidic water could induce a slight shift in the 5CB interfacial anchoring toward homeotropic, determined by a narrow, faint bright line at the 5CB–water interface. However, this bright appearance was entirely diminished following the injection of water with neutral pH, restoring the interface to a planar state. Thus, the influence of acidic pH on the 5CB anchoring was indeed temporary. As another control experiment, a 10 ppb MB flow was injected into a channel (Figure 2c). As anticipated, the planar anchoring of 5CB at the interface remained consistent because the water-soluble MB does not induce an observable ordering transition at the LC–water interface. Finally, to indicate that the nanoparticles predominantly facilitate the detection of MB molecules at the 5CB–water interface (as considered in Figure 1g), the interface was decorated with DMOAP F-SiNPs in an aqueous suspension with pH = 2. Subsequently, neutral pH water flow was introduced into the channel. In contrast to the experiment done with water at pH = 2 (see Figure 2b), the homeotropic state of the interface and its bright appearance remained unchanged following the injection of water with a neutral pH. Therefore, it can be inferred that the adsorbed nanoparticles at the 5CB–water interface serve as a crucial mediator for detecting species in the aqueous medium within microfluidic sensors through facilitating LC anchoring transitions.

Figure 2. (a) The representative sketch of a microfluidic channel geometry. Using the nanoparticle suspension at its initial pH of approximately 7 blocks the channel inlet, owing to the adsorption of positively charged DMOAP F-SiNPs to the glass-PDMS walls. Meanwhile, nanoparticle suspension with pH = 2 effectively eliminated the blockage. (b) The temporary effect of water with pH = 2 on the LC anchoring at the 5CB–water interface, clarified by rinsing the channel with neutral pH water. (c) The introduction of aqueous MB flow into the microchannel confirmed that MB molecules do not induce a direct ordering transition at the LC–water interface. (d) The polarized (P), brightfield (B), and fluorescence (F) optical micrographs of the 5CB–aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs with pH = 2 ($\sim 10^9$ particles/mL) system, showing that the homeotropic state of the interface remained unchanged following the injection of water with neutral pH due to the effective adsorption of nanoparticles to the interface. Scale bars: (a, b, c, d) 100 μm and 10 μm for the corresponding zoomed sections.

In addition to the microfluidic sensor experiments, we conducted experiments utilizing nanoparticle-assisted LC droplet sensors with an equivalent approach. As sketched in Figure 3a, 5CB droplet emulsions were prepared in suspensions of DMOAP F-SiNPs at pH = 2. After equilibration, specific concentrations of MB were added to the emulsion, and the steady-state configuration distributions of the 5CB droplets were subsequently investigated. It is worth noting that the determination of MB in aqueous solutions is not feasible using the bare aqueous interface of 5CB droplets. Therefore, to facilitate the observation of a configurational transition in 5CB droplets induced by MB dye, nanoparticles offer an interface that enhances the MB–nanoparticle–LC interactions. Figure 3b depicts the brightfield, polarized, and fluorescence microscopy images of a representative 5CB droplet in the presence of $\sim 10^9$ particles/mL of DMOAP F-SiNPs. The observations indicated that a layer of nanoparticles was effectively adsorbed at the droplet interface, attributed to the physical interaction between negatively charged 5CB and positively charged DMOAP F-SiNPs (supported by zeta potential measurements below). The locations of nanoparticles surrounding the interface of 5CB were shown by fluorescence confocal microscope (FCM) images obtained from the z-stack of the confocal micrographs (Figure 3c). Moreover, SEM

images of polymerized 5CB droplets revealed the presence of a dense packing of nanoparticles at the droplet interface (Figure 3d). The magnified images confirmed that the nanoparticles fully covered the LC interface. It is important to note that the wrinkling observed in the full coverage of nanoparticles at the droplet interface resulted from the shrinkage of the polymerized droplets following the leaching of the unreacted mesogens. This phenomenon has been thoroughly documented in the literature.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁹

The observed 5CB droplet configurations were categorized into three distinct groups, as exhibited in Figure 3e: *Bipolar* droplets, which arise from planar interfacial anchoring; *Preradial* droplets, encompassing a range of transitional states between bipolar and radial configurations (predominantly characterized by preradial configurations, along with a smaller number of escaped radial and axial droplets) originating from tilted interfacial anchoring; *Radial* droplets, which are formed due to the homeotropic interfacial anchoring of 5CB. As shown in Figure 3f, the initial $95.8 \pm 1\%$ bipolar configuration ($1.7 \pm 0.5\%$ radial) of droplets in water with $\text{pH} = 2$ was observed to decrease to $43.3 \pm 1.7\%$ bipolar configuration ($45.8 \pm 0.85\%$ radial) upon exposure to an acidic aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension. Adding MB at concentrations ranging from 0.01 to 10 ppb into the emulsion of 5CB within suspensions of DMOAP F-SiNPs at $\text{pH} = 2$ resulted in a response of droplets toward a progressive enhancement of bipolar configuration, accompanied by a corresponding reduction in radial configuration. Notably, the frequency of the bipolar configuration increased to $91.7 \pm 4.4\%$ and the radial configuration decreased to $4.2 \pm 0.6\%$. The values exhibited relative stability at a concentration of 10 ppb. We reasoned that the response of the droplets may originate from the partitioning of analyte molecules at the interfaces, which subsequently restricts the interaction between the DMOAP molecules and the 5CB. This limitation diminishes the likelihood of perpendicular alignment of the 5CB at the interfaces. Such an intermolecular phenomenon is likely to lead to an increase in bipolar droplet configurations, as planar interfacial anchoring becomes more probable. We clarify that the emulsions were not prepared by integrating 5CB droplets into nanoparticle suspensions preequilibrated with aqueous solutions of MB at specified concentrations. Instead, we introduced various concentrations of MB into the initially prepared “Pickering” emulsions of 5CB droplets decorated with DMOAP F-SiNPs. Thus, the results of nanoparticle-decorated LC droplet sensors provided in this study are equivalent to the approach we followed in the microfluidic experiments.

Figure 3. (a) The sketch of the experimental system of nanoparticle-decorated LC droplet sensors. (b) Brightfield (B), polarized (P), and fluorescence (F) microscopy images of a 5CB droplet in aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension with pH = 2 (~10⁹ particles/mL). (c) FCM images collected from the z-stack micrographs indicate the locations of nanoparticles surrounding an LC droplet. I to VI show a gradual radial movement from the outer surface to the center of the droplet. (d) SEM images of the polymerized LC droplets after contacting with ~10⁹ particles/mL DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension. The red, green, and purple squares represent the full coverage of the LC droplet with nanoparticles at different locations. (e) Brightfield and polarized light micrographs depict different 5C droplets corresponding to the bipolar, preradial, and radial director configurations as illustrated schematically. (f) Frequency of 5CB droplet configuration in aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension at pH = 2 (~10⁹ particles/mL) with added MB of 0.01, 0.1, 0.3, 0.8, 1, and 10 ppb. Scale bars: (b, c) 20 μ m, (d) 20 μ m for the LC droplet and 1 μ m for the magnified regions, (e) 5 μ m.

To find the limit of detection (LOD) of MB for the nanoparticle-decorated LC-interfaced flow sensors (prepared by ~10⁹ particles/mL of DMOAP F-SiNPs) within the microchannel platform, we investigated the response of 5CB at different concentrations of MB. Figure 4a indicates the

representative response of the nanoparticle-decorated 5CB–aqueous interfaces to various MB concentrations. Accompanying sketches of the average LC-director profiles are also provided to elucidate the underlying LC configurations in microfluidics, resulting in the shown optical appearances. Evidently, the nanoparticle-decorated 5CB interface remained unchanged following the injection of 0.1 ppb MB, while it exhibited a partial darkening upon the introduction of 0.3, 0.5, and 0.8 ppb of MB. The darkening process intensified with increasing MB concentration, attributed to the transition of additional regions from a homeotropic to a planar state, resulting from an enhanced adsorption of MB at the interface. Eventually, with the extinction of the homeotropic regions at the interface, the complete response occurred at 1 ppb MB.

To quantify responses from the microfluidic sensors, a signal formula derived from a generated function based on interfacial intensities (see Experimental) was utilized, demonstrating the MB concentration-dependent changes in the LC response. As highlighted in Figure 4b, the response of the microfluidic 5CB interface to the analyte reached its saturation at a concentration of 1 ppb and remained consistent beyond this threshold. In contrast, the average sensor response exhibited a gradual decline from 1 to 0.1 ppb, ultimately reaching less than 4% at a concentration of 0.1 ppb. Furthermore, no measurable response was detected at a concentration of 0.01 ppb. Accordingly, the LOD was found to be 0.1 ppb MB. Upon assessing the statistical analysis of the nanoparticle-assisted LC droplet sensors presented in Figure 3f, and applying a signal formula that accounts for the variations in the total number of preradial and radial droplets before and after adsorption of the analyte to the nanoparticle-decorated interface, it was revealed that the response curve for the droplet system utilizing the same $\sim 10^9$ particles/mL concentration of the nanoparticles exhibited a trend analogous to that observed in microfluidic sensor systems. These findings show that the LOD for the droplet systems sensor was about 0.1 ppb, which aligns with the microfluidic results as shown in Figure 4b.

Figure 4. (a) The polarized (P) optical micrographs, along with the corresponding sketches, depict the response of the nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensor ($\sim 10^9$ particles/mL of DMOAP F-SiNPs) to various MB concentrations. The dashed line in optical micrograph shows the location of the LC-aqueous interface. (b) The response plot of nanoparticle-decorated LC sensors in microchannel (left axis) and droplet (right axis) systems to a range of MB concentrations from 0.01 ppt to 10 ppb, highlighting the LOD of the sensors for varying concentrations of DMOAP F-SiNPs. I, Pr and R in y axes refer to intensity, preradial and radial, respectively. Scale bars: 100 μm for the polarized micrographs.

The results of the response experiments conducted in both microfluidic and droplet systems suggested that one potential response mechanism of the sensors stems from charge interactions occurring in two distinct stages. First, 5CB responds to the adsorption of the nanoparticles with a functionalized surface. Second, the nanoparticle-decorated 5CB interface responds to the adsorption of MB molecules. Utilizing zeta potential measurements provided evidences on the underlying mechanism. As illustrated in Figure 5a, the zeta potential of 5CB droplets was recorded as -49.3 ± 1.6 mV.⁵⁰⁻⁵³ It is known that the adsorption of nanoparticles at interfaces is significantly influenced by the charge characteristics and interfacial properties of the particles.^{50, 54} The bare F-SiNPs exhibited a zeta potential of -41.6 ± 1.2 mV. Following the functionalization of the nanoparticles with DMOAP, a zeta potential of $+30.7 \pm 0.4$ mV at pH = 2 was observed. These measurements were consistent with the past data.⁵⁰ The high positive zeta potential value encouraged the adsorption of the DMOAP functionalized nanoparticles onto the negatively charged interfaces of 5CB. This phenomenon was evidenced by the zeta potential of 5CB droplets emulsion prepared in an aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension at pH = 2, which was measured to be -1.7 ± 0.4 mV. The findings indicated that the adsorption of nanoparticles led to a significant reduction in the negative charge at the interfaces of 5CB, ultimately bringing the overall net interfacial charge close to neutrality. Consequently, there exists the potential for MB molecules to adsorb onto the nanoparticle-decorated 5CB–aqueous interface. This adsorption process is likely

to occur through various mechanisms, which will be elaborated upon in the subsequent discussion. Among these mechanisms, electrostatic interactions represent one of the plausible contributing factors. The SEM images presented in Figure 5b demonstrated that the density of the adsorbed nanoparticles at the interfaces of the 5CB droplets was significantly decreased when droplets were exposed to a less concentrated nanoparticle suspension. Specifically, in contrast to the full coverage of the droplet interfaces using $\sim 10^9$ particles/mL of DMOAP F-SiNPs (as illustrated in Figure 3d), exposure of 5CB droplets to 20x diluted nanoparticle suspension led to partial interfacial coverage. This observation prompted a critical question regarding the implications of partial interfacial coverage. To explore this further, we employed a 60x diluted aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension in the zeta potential measurements investigations. This dilution was adopted to ascertain the zeta potential of complex emulsions containing 5CB droplets, DMOAP F-SiNPs, and MB, as the use of diluted nanoparticle suspensions facilitated more accurate and reliable measurements. Figure 5a demonstrates that introducing 0.01 ppt MB to the emulsion of 5CB droplets prepared in an aqueous suspension of DMOAP F-SiNPs at pH = 2 resulted in a shift in the net interfacial charge toward a marginally positive value. The corresponding zeta potential was measured at $+0.5 \pm 0.2$ mV. Upon increasing the MB concentration, a slight enhancement in the zeta potential was observed. Notably, the zeta potential reached $+16.9 \pm 2.5$ mV at a concentration of 0.1 ppb MB. Control experiments also showed that adding 0.1 ppb MB to the nanoparticle suspensions did not change the zeta potential of DMOAP F-SiNPs due to electrostatic repulsion between the positively charged nanoparticles and MB molecules. Thus, we reasoned that the complex charging of the oil-water interfaces was critical in facilitating the interactions of the analytical species with the adsorbed nanoparticles at 5CB interfaces. In light of these findings, we sought to explore the detection of trace-level concentrations of MB utilizing nanoparticle-decorated LC sensors in both droplet systems and microchannels.

Figure 5. (a) Variation of zeta potential for the systems involving 5CB-in-water emulsion, 60x diluted aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension with pH = 2, and various concentrations of MB. (b) SEM images of the polymerized LC droplets after contacting with 20x diluted DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension. The partial coverage of LC droplets, including areas with adsorbed nanoparticles as well as regions devoid of them, is illustrated in two distinct zones identified by red and green squares. (c) Configuration distribution of Pickering emulsion of 5CB droplet in aqueous 20x diluted DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension at pH = 2 with added MB of 0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.1 and 1 ppb. Scale bars: (b) 20 μm for the LC droplet and 1 μm for the magnified region.

Nanoparticles formed a dense interface adsorbed phase, enforcing dominant anchoring across the entire surface. For homeotropic-inducing nanoparticles, this shifts the droplet predominantly to a radial configuration (as confirmed by the frequency of droplet configurations in Figure 3f). However, with partial coverage, the adsorption of nanoparticles on the surfaces of 5CB droplets was incomplete, resulting in a heterogeneous or "patchy" 5CB–aqueous interface. The presence of the nanoparticles created localized areas with altered interfacial energy and interfacial anchoring conditions, while the remaining nanoparticle-lean interface retained its original anchoring. This mismatch created localized elastic distortions in the nematic director field, manifesting as topological defects that served as energetic traps for nearby nanoparticles. As a result, nanoparticles migrated to regions of high elastic stress, trapped at defect sites, and formed aggregates.^{55, 56} These aggregates would subsequently lead to preradial configurations as a consequence of defect pinning.⁴⁸ The phenomenon elucidated the significant increase in the

frequency of preradial configurations relative to radial configurations in a Pickering emulsion composed of 5CB droplets within a 20x diluted aqueous nanoparticle suspension (Figure 5c). In the vicinity of defect regions, LC mesogens were susceptible to small perturbations because the director field was already distorted and energetically penalized. When an analyte adsorbs to the nanoparticles, it slightly alters the local anchoring strength or orientation. This minor local change propagates through the elastic LC matrix, resulting in a noticeable realignment that can amplify sensing signals. Pickering emulsions of 5CB droplets decorated with 20x diluted DMOAP F-SiNPs exhibited a response to analyte concentrations as low as 0.1 ppb (Figure 5c). The frequency of droplets in a preradial configuration began to decline at this concentration, as they transitioned to a bipolar state. However, through our investigations using microfluidics, we uncovered something truly noteworthy about continuous interfaces in terms of sensitivity, which we will elaborate on below.

To examine the response of the nanoparticle-decorated microfluidic LC-aqueous interfaces to lower concentrations of analyte in the aqueous medium (≤ 0.1 ppb, which is the LOD determined for $\sim 10^9$ particles/mL of DMOAP F-SiNPs), the 5CB-aqueous interface was decorated using 10x diluted DMOAP F-SiNPs, followed by the injection of a 0.1 ppb MB aqueous solution into the channel. These experiments were performed at low bulk and interfacial shear stress with equal inlet pressures to avoid high shear stress effects, aligning with prior experiments. The incubation of the channel using a 10x diluted nanoparticle suspension led to the formation of a thinner, bright appearance at the 5CB-water interface, compared to observations made with the concentrated nanosuspension. The polarized micrographs in Figure 6a indicate that the bright appearance of the 5CB-water interface progressively darkened over time as MB molecules adsorbed onto the nanoparticles, shifting to planar anchoring. The brightfield microscopy images also reflected this transition. The sensing process was completed in 25 min for a 0.1 ppb concentration of MB. In contrast to the fluorescence micrographs obtained from channels incubated with non-diluted nanosuspension, which revealed a substantial number of nanoparticles adsorbed to the 5CB-water interface as well as to the glass and PDMS surfaces in the bulk of aqueous media, the current experiments demonstrate a markedly reduced quantity of adsorbed nanoparticles. The interaction between MB molecules and these adsorbed nanoparticles, which served to stabilize their position at the 5CB-water interface, was responsible for the ordering transition in anchoring of 5CB to the planar state. At the end of the sensing process, rinsing the channel with fresh water provided

evidence of the reversibility of the system. During this process, the nanoparticles remained positioned at the interface, while the dye molecules previously adsorbed onto the nanoparticle-decorated 5CB interface were effectively desorbed and carried away by the flowing water. This desorption triggered a transition in the 5CB anchoring from a planar to a homeotropic/tilted anchoring, resulting in the particle-decorated 5CB–water interface exhibiting a bright appearance under a polarized optical microscope (Figure 6b). Figure 6c indicates the ultimate response of a 10x diluted nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensor to various trace-level concentrations of MB. Corresponding sketches are included as well to clarify the mechanism that drives the responses. The thin, bright layer arose from the interfacial homeotropic/tilted alignment of 5CB, resulting from the partial adsorption of diluted nanoparticles at the interface along the glass side (to be discussed later). The nanoparticle-decorated 5CB–aqueous interface showed no change with the introduction of 0.05 ppt of MB. However, a partial darkening was observed after the injection of 0.1 ppt of MB. The increased adsorption of MB molecules at the interface resulted in a transition to a planar anchoring, achieving a complete response at a concentration of 1 ppt of MB.

Figure 6. (a) Response of the nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensor (10x diluted DMOAP F-SiNPs) to 0.1 ppb MB concentration over time, showing the orientational ordering transition of the interface from homeotropic/tilted to planar anchoring upon adsorption of MB molecules to the interface in 25 min. (b) Washing the channel with water after the sensing process shows the reversibility of the system, enabling the interface to revert to the homeotropic/tilted state upon analyte elimination. (c) The polarized optical

micrographs, accompanied by the corresponding sketches, illustrate the definitive response of the 10x diluted nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensor to various ultralow MB concentrations. Scale bars: 100 μm for the polarized (P), brightfield (B), and fluorescence (F) micrographs and 10 μm for their zoomed parts.

As presented in Figure 4b, a decrease in the MB concentration from 0.1 ppb to 1 ppt resulted in the sensor maintaining a robust response to the analyte. Subsequent reductions in MB concentration led to a decline in the average sensor response, ultimately diminishing to less than 3% at a concentration of 0.05 ppt. Therefore, a ten-fold dilution of nanoparticles during the microfluidic experiments achieved a substantial decrease in the LOD by three orders of magnitude. To further investigate the assessment of nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensors in response to ultralow concentrations of MB, we utilized nanoparticles diluted to 20x and 30x within the sensors. It was observed that in the case of 10x diluted nanoparticles, the average response of 5CB to MB decreased to approximately 60% at a concentration of 0.1 ppt of the analyte. Conversely, both the 20x and 30x diluted nanoparticles sustained their maximum response value at the same concentration. Furthermore, the LOD of sensors utilizing 20x and 30x diluted nanoparticles decreased to 0.03 and 0.01 ppt of MB, respectively. It can be concluded from Figure 4b that a 10 to 30-fold dilution of aqueous $\sim 10^9$ particles/mL of DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension significantly shifts the maximum response of the microfluidic sensors to ultralow concentrations of the analyte and decreases the LOD of the sensors by four orders of magnitude. The results obtained for the diluted nanoparticle suspensions, particularly those at 20x and 30x dilutions, were found to be closely aligned (Figure 4b). Consequently, further dilution of the nanosuspension is unlikely to yield significant outcomes. This observation was confirmed through experiments conducted up to 100x diluted nanosuspensions.

In essence, we showed that in terms of achieving highly sensitive nanoparticle-integrated LC-based sensors, soft interfaced continuous systems in microfluidic platforms act as a wizard that facilitates the detection of analytes at trace-level concentrations in water, featuring sharp changes in the easily-observable optical output. At this stage, the fundamental questions that emerge are:

- (i) *What are the underlying mechanisms that explain how nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensors respond when subjected to both concentrated and diluted nanoparticle solutions?*
- (ii) *What is the selectivity profile of the developed sensor when exposed to diverse analytes in an aqueous environment?*

To comprehensively address these inquiries, we undertook a series of supporting experiments, the findings of which are detailed along with the discussion of the critical role of the nanoparticle-decorated interfaces of microfluidic LC systems.

The development of microfluidic systems, in which $\sim 10^9$ particles/mL of DMOAP F-SiNPs were used to decorate at the 5CB–aqueous interface, has facilitated the creation of a sensor platform capable of effectively detecting analytes that do not induce a direct ordering transition, specifically shown with the MB model molecule, with a low LOD of 0.1 ppb. Significantly, the introduction of diluted nanoparticle suspensions ranging from 10 to 30-fold to decorate the interface resulted in microfluidic sensors capable of responding to ultralow analyte concentrations, achieving four orders of magnitude reduction in the LOD. It is reasoned that such a remarkable enhancement in sensor performance can be fundamentally linked to the structures of the LC–aqueous interface, specifically to the localization of the nanoparticles at the interface. Using fluorescence confocal polarizing microscope (FCPM) imaging collected at the mid-planes of the channels, we were able to conduct a thorough investigation of the 5CB–aqueous phase interface in the absence and presence of nanoparticles at different concentrations, as well as the response of the nanoparticle-decorated 5CB–aqueous interface flow sensor to the analyte. The polarized, brightfield, and FCPM micrographs exhibited in column I of Figure 7 illustrated the planar anchoring of 5CB at the interface. In addition, z-stack cross-sectional FCPM images collected at 0° and 90° polarization of the fluorescence excitation light revealed that the interface was not flat and displayed a minor, slightly curved inclination. Upon the decoration of the interface with suspensions of $\sim 10^9$ particles/mL DMOAP F-SiNPs, a thick, bright layer was formed at the interface, as depicted in the polarized, brightfield, and FCPM images presented in column II of Figure 7. This thick layer indicated the homeotropic anchoring of 5CB, resulting from the considerable adsorption of nanoparticles at the interface. The presence of the bright layer was also evident in the z-stack FCPM image obtained at 90° polarization of the fluorescence excitation light (shown with a yellow arrow in the micrograph). The 3D view of the 5CB–aqueous interface obtained from z-stack FCM imaging supports the formation of a layer of nanoparticles at the inclined interface. The distribution of nanoparticles was effectively observed between the glass and PDMS; however, the adsorption on the glass side was more pronounced, where aggregations of nanoparticles also formed. We associated this with several factors, including the interaction of silanol groups with a higher density on the glass surface, which covalently bond with the trimethoxysilane groups of DMOAP

surrounding the nanoparticles. Additionally, gravity plays a role due to the aggregation of the nanoparticles, as well as the strain on the LC side that would facilitate particle motion toward the glass interface, induced by elastic energy resulting from anchoring. The thick, bright appearance of the 5CB–aqueous interface completely faded following the adsorption of MB molecules onto the nanoparticles at the interface, as shown in column III of Figure 7. The 3D structure of the 5CB–aqueous interface obtained from z-stack FCM imaging indicated the presence of nanoparticles at the interface after the MB injection. The layer of nanoparticles was observed to be less intense compared to the one depicted in the 3D image in column II. This can be attributed to the minor replacement of nanoparticles, which occurred as a result of disturbing the system during the exchange of the nanoparticle suspension and analyte solution inlets. However, this does not explain the observed response, as the quantity of adsorbed nanoparticles remained quite sufficient to induce homeotropic interfacial anchoring at the 5CB–aqueous interface.

In order to comprehend the adsorption of nanoparticles at the interface and analyze the subsequent response of the nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensor in relation to the quantity of MB molecules, we conducted a numerical evaluation, which is briefly described as follows. Considering the effective 5CB–aqueous interface as a flat plane measuring 1.5 mm in length and 14 μm in width (depth of the microchannels), we calculated that 5×10^6 particles with an average size of 70 nm can accommodate the interface to establish a close-packed monolayer of nanoparticles. A total of 50 μL of the aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension, with a concentration of $\sim 10^9$ particles/mL, was employed to coat the interface. Consequently, this resulted in the presence of 5×10^7 particles within the microchannel, which was adequate for the formation of a monolayer. Excessive nanoparticles may accumulate at the interface, particularly along the glass side, while some adsorb to the glass-PDMS walls or are expelled from the outlet. Recently, we have shown that nanoparticle-assisted LC droplet sensors respond to the sub-ppb level concentrations of the analytes in aqueous medium, which corresponds to an interfacial coverage that is around 20% of a monolayer coverage at the interface of nanoparticles.³² Accordingly, the total number of MB molecules required to cover 20% of the interfacial area of the adsorbed monolayer of nanoparticles was 1.5×10^{10} molecules. About 50 μL of 1 ppb MB, the threshold concentration that yielded a complete sensor response to the analyte, was consumed during the detection experiments. Hence, there were 9.4×10^{10} molecules of MB within the microchannel, which were effectively able to

interact with the nanoparticles at the 5CB–aqueous interface. This interaction induced a transition in the interfacial orientational ordering of 5CB from homeotropic to planar anchoring.

The polarized, brightfield, and FCPM micrographs illustrated in column IV of Figure 7 showed that decorating the interface using a 20x dilution of aqueous $\sim 10^9$ particles/mL of DMOAP F-SiNPs suspension led to the formation of a thin, bright layer at the interface. The z-stack FCPM image obtained at 90° polarization of the fluorescence excitation light also reflected the presence of this bright layer (shown with a yellow arrow in the micrograph). The observed thinner bright layer (compared to column II) originated from the localized director field straining of 5CB, caused by the localized adsorption of nanoparticles at the interface along the glass side, as evidenced by the 3D presentation of the z-stack FCM imaging conducted at the 5CB–aqueous interface. Upon the adsorption of MB onto the nanoparticles at the interface, as illustrated in column V of Figure 7, the bright appearance of the 5CB–aqueous interface entirely vanished. The 3D structure of the z-stack FCM image confirmed the presence of nanoparticles at the interface during the response to the analyte, where MB molecules interacted with the nanoparticles, resulting in an ordering transition of 5CB to planar anchoring. The substantial decrease (by one order of magnitude) in the number of nanoparticles notably restricts the formation of a monolayer within the microchannel. Specifically, in 50 μL of 20x diluted nanoparticle suspensions, the total quantity of available nanoparticles corresponds to one close-packed monolayer of nanoparticles at the interface. A considerable amount of these particles was lost through the channel due to adherence to the glass walls or expulsion from the outlet. The remaining nanoparticles tend to preferentially adsorb to the interface along the glass side rather than the PDMS side, as previously explained. The 3D visualization of the z-stack FCM image displayed in column IV of Figure 7 verifies that the adsorption of nanoparticles to the glass side of the interface was minimal. Thus, 9.4×10^6 molecules of MB, equivalent to 50 μL of 0.1 ppt MB— the threshold analyte concentration for complete sensor response— was sufficient for interaction with the nanoparticles at the 5CB–aqueous interface. This interaction caused a shift in the orientational ordering of the LC from homeotropic/tilted to planar anchoring.

Figure 7. The (a) polarized (P), (b) brightfield (B), and (c) fluorescence confocal polarizing microscope (FCPM) images (taken from mid-planes) of five systems including the (I) 5CB–water, (II) 5CB–aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs with pH = 2 ($\sim 10^9$ particles/mL), (III) the nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensor ($\sim 10^9$ particles/mL of DMOAP F-SiNPs) responding to 1 ppb MB concentration, (IV) 5CB–aqueous 20x diluted DMOAP F-SiNPs with pH = 2, and (V) the nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensor (20x diluted DMOAP F-SiNPs) responding to 0.1 ppt MB concentration. The images show the transition of orientational ordering at the 5CB–water interface from planar to homeotropic/tilted anchoring with concentrated and diluted nanoparticles, respectively, and shifting to planar after the nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensors respond to MB. (d) Z-stack cross-sectional FCPM images of 5CB (with 0.01% Nile red fluorophore) at the aqueous interface (found to be inclined) acquired at 0° and 90° polarization of the fluorescence excitation light. (e) The 3D structure of the 5CB–aqueous interface obtained from z-stack FCM imaging, demonstrating the distribution of nanoparticles at the inclined interface. Scale bars: (a, b, c) 10 μm , (d) 5 μm .

Based on the structural characterizations carried out employing FCPM and FCM images above, and strengthened by Z-stack cross-sectional FCM micrographs of fluorescent nanoparticles, we sketched the proposed LC director configurations, as depicted in Figure 8, which also summarized the response mechanism of the nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensors. The planar anchoring of 5CB at the interface of pure water was shown earlier in Figure 1c. The interface was found to maintain an inclination with a slight curvature through FCPM images. Figure 8a demonstrates the perpendicular alignment of 5CB at the interface after decoration of the interface with a concentrated nanosuspension. The analysis of the x-z and y-z views of the z-stack FCM micrographs revealed that the resulting homeotropic anchoring was ascribed to the full coverage of the interface with nanoparticles. This full coverage, along with the inclination of the interface, substantiated the observation of a double line of nanoparticles in sensing experiments (Figures 1e, g, h, and 2d) when examining the microchannels from the top (x-y view). Specifically, the lower

and upper lines correspond to the adsorbed nanoparticle aggregates at the glass and the PDMS contact lines of the interface, respectively. Following the adsorption of MB molecules to the interface in the presence of nanoparticles, the orientational ordering of the 5CB–aqueous phase shifted from homeotropic to planar anchoring (Figure 8b). Treating the microchannel with 20x diluted nanoparticle suspensions resulted in the localization of interface-adsorbed nanoparticles along the glass-contact line, as shown in Figure 8c. This phenomenon explained the observation of a single line of nanoparticles in the sensing experiments (Figures 6a, b), in contrast to the appearance observed with non-diluted nanoparticles. Accordingly, LC ordering was locally strained to possess bend distortions as shown in Figure 8c. Upon the adsorption of MB onto the nanoparticles at the interface, the interfacial anchoring of LC switched to a planar state as sketched in Figure 8d.

Figure 8. Representative sketches of the LC director profiles under weak flow conditions, which are delineated based on the distribution of nanoparticles at the interface, as derived from z-stack FCM micrographs (x-z and y-z views) for (a) 5CB–aqueous DMOAP F-SiNPs with $\text{pH} = 2$ ($\sim 10^9$ particles/mL), (b) the nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensor ($\sim 10^9$ particles/mL of DMOAP F-SiNPs) responding to 1 ppb MB concentration, (c) 5CB–aqueous 20x diluted DMOAP F-SiNPs with $\text{pH} = 2$, and (d) the nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensor (20x diluted DMOAP F-SiNPs) responding to 0.1 ppt MB concentration. Scale bars: 5 μm for z-stack micrographs.

In addition to high sensitivity, a sensor platform with favorable selectivity for target molecules can be employed across a wide range of applications, including the detection of micropollutants in aqueous environments and medical diagnostics. To address this issue, we conducted comprehensive experiments to evaluate the selectivity of the 20x diluted nanoparticle-decorated LC–aqueous interfaced flow sensors. The response of the sensor to a range of analytes, including

dyes, micropollutants (such as pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs) and industrial chemicals), a protein, and amino acids, was analyzed through these experiments (Table 1). Among the employed model analytes, the 20x diluted nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensors responded to concentrations ≥ 0.1 ppt of MB, Acridine Orange, Nile Red, Diclofenac, Indomethacin sodium hydrate, and perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA). As a plausible mechanism, we have already demonstrated through zeta potential measurements that the analyte adsorbs onto the nanoparticle-decorated LC interface via electrostatic interactions. However, a thorough analysis of the characteristics of these molecules provided further insights into the interactions between the responding analytes and the nanoparticle-decorated LC interface. Notably, we found that hydrophobic interactions and π - π stacking can also play roles in the response of the sensors to these analytes. We noticed that each of these analytes possesses hydrophobic regions, including aromatic rings within their chemical structures (except PFOA, which contains a perfluorinated hydrophobic region). Specifically, MB and Acridine Orange have three fused rings, Nile Red possesses four fused rings, Diclofenac consists of dichlorophenyl and phenylacetic acid groups, and Indomethacin features an indole core with p-chlorobenzoyl substituent. The aromatic groups of all five compounds can interact with hydrophobic biphenyl and pentyl chains of 5CB, as well as engage in π - π stacking with the biphenyl system of 5CB molecules at the nanoparticle interface. We explain this hypothesis as follows. The 20x diluted nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensors were characterized by the localized bent distortions of the 5CB director field at the interface because of the localized adsorption of nanoparticles. When analytes with planar aromatic structures adsorb at the interface, they would tend to position flat on the aqueous phase, likely due to the entropy-driven preference to maximize interface contact. This arrangement may not align ideally with the homeotropic 5CB, potentially encouraging the mesogens to reorient more parallel to the interface to maintain and stabilize π - π interactions. As more analytes accumulate over time, this effect could gradually promote a shift to planar anchoring. Moreover, PFOA establishes a strong electrostatic interaction with DMOAP-coated nanoparticles and can adsorb at the LC-water interface. Its carboxylate head faces the aqueous phase, while the fluorinated tail aligns with the hydrophobic region. Due to the incompatibility between perfluorinated tails and hydrocarbon alkyl chains of DMOAP or hydrocarbon parts of 5CB, PFOA forms a mismatched interfacial film rather than embedding deeply. This surfactant-like layer induces a transition in the ordering of 5CB to a planar state.

Further, the sensor exhibited partial responses to concentrations of 0.1-10 ppt for Ampicillin sodium salt, Ochratoxin A, Methyl Orange, and L-Leucine. These compounds also contain hydrophobic aromatic rings within their chemical structures (except L-Leucine, which possesses a hydrophobic aliphatic chain). In detail, Ampicillin sodium salt has a phenyl ring, Ochratoxin A consists of a chlorinated phenyl ring and an isocoumarin ring system, and Methyl Orange includes two benzene rings. Similarly, the partial response of the sensor at this concentration to these analytes can be attributed to electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions, as well as π - π stacking between the analytes containing aromatics and the 5CB. In this case, local distortions occur in the 5CB anchoring, resulting in a partial ordering transition of 5CB to planar anchoring. Moreover, it was observed that the sensor did not respond to analytes such as Erythromycin, BSA, L-Serine, and L-Aspartic acid. These compounds either have no aromatic groups (or limited accessible aromatics for BSA) in their chemical structure or are highly soluble in water. It can be concluded that the diluted nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensors exhibit a selective response toward various analytes. These sensors demonstrate a full or partial response to amphiphilic molecules characterized by hydrophobic/aromatic regions. Conversely, they are unable to respond to highly hydrophilic analytes that possess significant solubility in water and lack hydrophobic/aromatic structures within their composition.

Recently, Wang et al.⁵⁷ have reported a machine learning-assisted LC droplet array platform for the sensitive and selective detection of two amphiphilic per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), including PFOA and perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) in water at concentrations as low as 1 and 3.5 parts per trillion (ppt) for PFOA and PFOS, respectively. By developing an autoencoder neural network, they were able to capture the essential characteristics of LC droplet arrays treated with water samples containing various concentrations of PFOA and subsequently used the output latent space to train a basic classifier network. They showed that although low concentrations of these analytes do not lead to changes in the optical appearances of the LC droplets that are discernible or diagnostic to the trained human eye, the neural network is capable of extracting valuable information to predict their presence accurately. In terms of advancement in this research, our nanoparticle-integrated LC-based microfluidics sensors were able to (i) enhance the sensitivity limit of PFOA to 0.1 ppt and (ii) exhibit very apparent changes in the optical characteristics of LC in the vicinity of nanoparticle-decorated interface that can be identified by

the naked-eye, and (iii) introduce selectivity based on the details of the chemical structures of the analytical targets.

3. CONCLUSION

This work introduced nanoparticle-integrated LC-based sensors featuring high sensitivity, facilitated through engineered soft interface continuous systems in microfluidic platforms. Using FCM images, the adsorption characteristics and positioning of DMOAP F-SiNPs at the LC–aqueous phase interface were successfully tracked. We demonstrated that decorating the LC–aqueous interface with full coverage of the interface exhibited response with a LOD of 0.1 ppb. Reducing the concentration of adsorbed nanoparticles at the interface can significantly enhance the sensor's performance in detecting trace-level concentrations of analytes. Accordingly, the incorporation of nanoparticles at dilutions ranging from 10 to 30-fold at the interface resulted in microfluidic sensors capable of responding to ultralow analyte concentrations, achieving the LOD as extremely low as 0.01-0.1 ppt. Such outstanding response performance, which, to our knowledge, is significantly challenging with many other reported methods, originates from the localized straining of the LC director, caused by the partial adsorption of nanoparticles at the interface along the contact line. The sensor is also powered by a considerable selectivity in detecting a range of analytes in water that do not induce an ordering transition upon direct adsorption to the LC interface from the aqueous phase. In detail, the analytes include amphiphilic molecules characterized by hydrophobic/aromatic regions. We believe our developed nanoparticle-integrated LC-based microfluidic sensors are ideal candidates for the broad range of real-time or periodic monitoring applications, including the detection of micropollutants present in aquatic systems and personal diagnostics. As we showed that the selectivity of the sensor response originated from the details in the interactions of the analyte molecule and the chemistries of the nanoparticle interfaces and the mesogenic constituents of the LC phase, the next step towards developing applications would be to engineer their chemistries (both nanoparticle interfaces and LC mesogens) towards specific analytical species.

Table 1. The selectivity of 20x diluted nanoparticle-decorated LC flow sensors toward the detection of various analytes

Compound	Type / Source	Charge	Water Affinity	Chemical Structure	Examined Conc. (ppt)	Response Status	Hazard Risks / Purpose of Use in This Study
Methylene Blue (MB)*	Dye (Industrial pollutant)	Positive	Hydrophilic		0.1	Yes	Harms photosynthesis and poses health risks to humans, including cyanosis, tissue necrosis, and jaundice. ^{58, 59}
Acridine Orange*	Dye (Industrial pollutant)	Positive	Amphiphilic		0.1	Yes	Associated with mutagenic and carcinogenic effects. ^{60, 61}
Nile Red	Dye	Neutral	Hydrophobic		0.1	Yes	Model for conceptualizing the sensor
Diclofenac*	PPCPs	Negative	Amphiphilic		0.1	Yes	Categorized in Class 1: high priority pharmaceutical water pollutants. ^{1, 62}
Indomethacin sodium hydrate	PPCPs	Negative	Hydrophilic		0.1	Yes	Damages to the central nervous system, digestive system, and urinary system. ⁶³
Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)*	Industrial Chemical	Negative	Amphiphilic		0.1	Yes	Linked to plastic pollution, disrupts the endocrine system, leading to a wide range of toxic effects and public health risks. ⁶⁴
Ampicillin sodium salt	PPCPs	Negative	Hydrophilic		0.1–1	Partial	Antibiotic resistance and ecological toxicity. ⁶⁵
Ochratoxin A*	Mycotoxin	Negative	Predominantly hydrophobic		0.1–10	Partial	Exhibits a range of toxic effects, including hepatotoxicity, teratogenicity, and neurotoxicity, with a primary impact on kidney function. ⁶⁶
Methyl Orange	Dye (Industrial pollutant)	Negative	Hydrophilic		0.1–1	Partial	Inhibits photosynthesis and decreases oxygen production, poses health risks to humans, including skin allergies, cancer, and mutations. ⁶⁷
L-Leucine*	Amino Acid	Zwitterionic	Hydrophobic		0.1–10	Partial	Model for conceptualizing the sensor
Erythromycin*	PPCPs	Neutral	Amphiphilic		0.1–10	No	Nonbiodegradable, causes antibiotic resistance. ⁶⁸
Bovine serum albumin (BSA)	Protein	Negative	Hydrophilic		0.1–10	No	Model for conceptualizing the sensor
L-Serine	Amino Acid	Zwitterionic	Hydrophilic		0.1–1	No	Model for conceptualizing the sensor
L-Aspartic acid*	Amino Acid	Negative	Hydrophilic		0.1–10	No	Model for conceptualizing the sensor

* The response experiments for these analytes were conducted at least three times.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS

4.1. Materials

The primary reagents utilized in the synthesis of nanoparticles included tetraethoxysilane (TEOS), fluorescein 5-isothiocyanate (FITC) and (3-aminopropyl) triethoxysilane (APTES). Additional high-purity grade reagents and solvents employed in the synthesis process encompassed absolute ethanol, aqueous ammonia solutions (25%), cyclohexane, *n*-hexanol, and *t*-octylphenol polyethoxylate ether (Triton X-100). All reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA) and were used without further purification. The room temperature nematic liquid crystal 4-cyano-4'-pentylbiphenyl (5CB) and reactive monomer 4-(3-acryloyoxypropoxy) benzoic acid 2-methyl-1, 4-phenylene ester (RM257) were obtained from HCCH Jiangsu Hecheng Chemical Materials Co., Ltd. (Nanjing, China). HPLC-grade acetone, 2-propanol, toluene, trichloro(octadecyl)silane (OTS), dimethyloctadecyl[3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl]ammonium chloride (DMOAP), Photoinitiator 2,2-dimethoxy-2-phenylacetophenone (DMPAP), and Nile Red dye were received from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Deionized water (DW) was generated by a Heal Force water purification system, achieving a resistivity of 18.2 M Ω .cm. The positive photoresist AZ P4620, along with AZ EBR solvent, AZ 400 K developer 1:4, and buffered oxide etchant 7:1 (BOE), were sourced from Microchemicals GmbH (Ulm, Germany). Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) SylgardTM 184 Silicone Elastomer Kit was supplied from Dow Europe GmbH (Wiesbaden, Germany). Glass slides were purchased from Marienfeld GmbH (Lauda-Königshofen, Germany). Coverslips were obtained from ISOLAB Laborgeräte GmbH (Eschau, Germany). The chemicals listed in Table 1, used as analytes in this study, were sourced as follows: Methylene blue (MB) and Methyl Orange were received from Merck. Acridine Orange was purchased from BLDpharm (Shanghai, China). Diclofenac was obtained from Acros Organics (Geel, Belgium). Indomethacin sodium hydrate was acquired from MedChemExpress (New Jersey, USA). PFOA, Ampicillin sodium salt, Ochratoxin A, Erythromycin, BSA, L-Leucine, L-Serine and L-Aspartic acid were sourced from Sigma-Aldrich.

4.2. Synthesis of Core-Shell Fluorescent Silica Nanoparticles (F-SiNPs)

The fluorescent nanoparticles synthesized in this work comprise a core of the fluorophore (FITC), surrounded by a shell featuring silanol and siloxane functional groups. FITC has been reported to

exhibit substantial fluorescence intensity and photostability, retaining these characteristics even after a month of exposure to white light irradiation.⁶⁹⁻⁷¹

The methodology employed for the synthesis of fluorescent SiNPs was based on the water-in-oil reverse microemulsion technique documented in the literature.^{69, 72, 73} Initially, a fluorescein-based silane was prepared through the reaction of FITC and APTES via the formation of thiourea (SC(NH)₂) linkage. This reaction was carried out in absolute ethanol with continuous magnetic stirring for 12 h, under dark conditions at room temperature. Water-in-oil microemulsion was formed by mixing cyclohexane, *n*-hexanol, Triton X-100, and DW, followed by stirring the mixture for 30 min. The fluorescent precursor solution was then introduced dropwise into the microemulsion under magnetic stirring for 15 min at ambient temperature. Silica polymerization was initiated through the simultaneous addition of TEOS and NH₄OH 25% (serving as a catalyst) into the reaction mixture. Upon completion of the reaction after 20 h, the microemulsion system was disrupted by the addition of a 1:1 (v/v) DW:acetone solution, allowing for the subsequent isolation of nanoparticles from the suspension. The synthesized particles were centrifuged (10000 rpm, 10 min) using a Hettich Universal 320 centrifuge and washed several times with ethanol, acetone, and DW to remove surfactant and unreacted species. The resulting slurry of nanoparticles was then resuspended and preserved in DW. The amounts of materials used at various stages of the synthesis process are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The specific amounts of chemicals used at each stage of the F-SiNPs synthesis process.

Synthesis Stage	Chemicals	Amount
Fluorescent precursor solution	FITC	6 (mg)
	APTES	14.3 (mg)
	Absolute EtOH	3 (mL)
Microemulsion	Cyclohexane	94 (mL)
	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	22 (mL)
	Triton x-100	22 (mL)
	DW	6.7 (mL)
Reaction	NH ₄ OH 25%	0.90 (mL)
	TEOS	1.2 (mL)

4.3. Interfacial Functionalization of F-SiNPs with DMOAP

1 vol % DMOAP was added to the synthesized aqueous suspension of F-SiNPs and sonicated in an ultrasonic bath for 15 min. The DMOAP-functionalized F-SiNPs were isolated from the medium through centrifugation (10000 rpm, 10 min). The supernatant was replaced with DW, and the particles were redispersed in the aqueous phase using sonication. The centrifugation-redispersion process was repeated at least ten times to ensure the thorough removal of the unreacted silane molecules.

4.4. Preparation of Analyte Solutions

A 1 ppm stock solution of a chemical used as an analyte in the sensor response experiments was prepared by dissolving 0.5 mg of the chemical in 500 mL of ultrapure water. To prepare a 2 mL solution with a concentration of 10 ppb, 20 μ L of the stock solution was diluted in 1980 μ L of water. Subsequently, a 2 mL solution with a concentration of 1 ppb was prepared by taking 200 μ L of the 10 ppb solution and diluting it in 1800 μ L of water. Similarly, the process of serial dilution was carried out until reaching a concentration of 0.01 ppt.

4.5. Preparation of LC-in-Water Emulsion

To prepare LC-in-water emulsions, 3 μ L of 5CB was introduced into a vial containing 1 mL of an aqueous F-SiNPs suspension. The formation of 5CB droplets was achieved by subjecting the mixture to vortex mixing for 30 s at 3000 rpm.

4.6. Preparation of Nanoparticle-Decorated Polymerized LC Droplets

RM257-5CB mesogens mixture was prepared by mixing 75 wt % 5CB, 25 wt % RM257, and 1 wt % photoinitiator DMPAP and homogenizing into toluene as a cosolvent, using a vortex mixture.^{45, 74} Keeping the emulsion in the darkness, toluene was allowed to evaporate naturally to obtain the reactive mesogens mixture. 3 μ L of this mixture was used to prepare the LC-in-water emulsion, as explained earlier. Following the formation of the emulsion and subsequent adsorption of nanoparticles, LC droplets were polymerized under a 365 nm UV light source for 30 min. Free nanoparticles and unreacted mesogens were then removed by rinsing the emulsion at least three times with ethanol. The extraction process during rinsing was performed through natural sedimentation.

4.7. Characterization Techniques

Optical characterizations of LC droplet configurations were conducted using a polarized optical microscope, specifically the Olympus BX53 (Tokyo, Japan), which is equipped with a 50x objective. DLS, zeta potential, and concentration measurements of the synthesized nanoparticles, as well as the zeta potential analysis of LC-in-water emulsions, were carried out using Zetasizer Ultra (Malvern Instruments Ltd., US).

The responses of the microfluidic 5CB interfaces to analytes were quantified using Fiji ImageJ, an open-source software designed for image analysis. To this end, we measured the intensity of 5CB bulk flow (i_{Ref}), as well as the mean intensities of 5CB–aqueous interface upon the decoration of the interface with the nanoparticles (i_{NPs}) and after the adsorption of analytes (i_A). Applying a signal formula (equation 1) derived from a generated function based on interfacial intensities, the response (R) of LC to various concentrations of analytes was calculated. In this equation, I_A and I_{NPs} represent the differences between the corresponding interfacial intensities and the i_{Ref} .

$$R_{(Microfluidics)} = \frac{-(I_A - I_{NPs})}{I_{NPs}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The responses of LC droplet-based sensors were quantified using a generated signal formula (equation 2) that accounts for the variations in the total number of preradial and radial droplets following the decoration of 5CB droplets with nanoparticles and after the adsorption of analytes, represented as $(Pr + R)_{NPs}$ and $(Pr + R)_A$, respectively.

$$R_{(Droplets)} = \frac{-[(Pr + R)_A - (Pr + R)_{NPs}]}{(Pr + R)_{NPs}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

4.8. Fabrication of Microchannels on Glass Slides

As shown in Figure 2a, the sketch of the channel used in the lithography process consists of two inlets and two outlet ports that combine at the main channel with 400 μm in width and 1.5 cm in length, facilitating the co-flow of the nematic 5CB with an aqueous phase. Figure 9(a-f) illustrates the comprehensive fabrication procedure for microfluidic channels on glass slides. Initially, the glass slides underwent sonication in acetone and 2-propanol for 15 min each to ensure thorough cleaning. To promote hydrophobicity and enhance the attachment of the photoresist during the wet etching process, the glasses were immersed in a 1% vol DMOAP aqueous solution and sonicated

for 15 min. Subsequently, they were rinsed with water, absolute ethanol and 2-propanol, then dried with nitrogen. The positive photoresist AZ P4620 was diluted with EBR solvent in a 2:1 ratio and applied to DMOAP-treated glass slides with a spin coater (POLOS Spin 150i, SPS-Europe B.V., Putten, The Netherlands). A uniform photoresist coating was achieved using the spin coater set to a rotational speed of 1000 rpm for 50 s, with 10 s each for linear acceleration and deceleration. The glass slides coated with photoresist were soft baked on a hot plate at 110 °C for 50 seconds, cooled to room temperature naturally, and allowed to equilibrate for 10 minutes. A maskless photolithography system, the Polos NanoWriter equipped with a 405 nm laser (SPS-Europe B.V., Putten, The Netherlands), was employed to transfer the microchannel pattern onto the photoresist-coated substrates with an exposure UV dose of 160 mJ/cm². Next, the patterned glass slides were developed using the AZ 400 K developer solution for 80 s, followed by hard baking on a hot plate at 110 °C for 90 min. They were then allowed to cool to room temperature and equilibrated for at least two hours. The isotropic wet etching process involved placing glass slides vertically in a PTFE beaker containing a 7:1 buffered oxide etch (BOE) solution. The slides were etched in an ultrasonic bath for 20 minutes to create channels with a depth of 14 μm, corresponding to a consistent etching rate of 700 nm/min. In order to achieve smooth and consistent etching of channel edges, the temperature of the etching process was carefully maintained not to exceed 28 °C. Afterward, the glass slides underwent a two-step rinsing process in deionized water, followed by immersion in acetone to remove the photoresist. This stripping procedure was conducted using an ultrasonic bath for 20 min. They were then promptly rinsed in succession with acetone, DW, and 2-propanol to eliminate any surface residues. Finally, the glass slides were dried with nitrogen to prepare them for glass-PDMS bonding.

To prepare PDMS, 10 wt % of curing agent was added dropwise to the elastomer base and mixed for 5 min to ensure uniformity. The mixture was subjected to a vacuum for 30 min to facilitate the removal of any trapped air bubbles. Flat PDMS molds were fabricated using aluminum foil and glass slides coated with OTS, which was deposited in a vacuum desiccator for 30 min prior to use. The transparent PDMS mixture was cast onto the prepared molds and heated for 2 h at 60 °C in an oven. Following the cooling of the molds to ambient temperature, an etched glass slide was bonded to a flat PDMS elastomer of an appropriate size, which had been prepared using a 1.5 mm biopsy punch for the inlet and outlet ports of the channels. The bonding of glass and PDMS was achieved through oxygen plasma treatment, using the Diener Electronics (Ebhausen, Germany) device. The

PDMS surface and etched glass were exposed to an oxygen stream for 30 s under vacuum, with the chamber pre-vacuumed for 2 minutes. This was followed by a 20 s application of plasma and gas ventilation. Subsequently, the etched glass slide and PDMS elastomer were bonded to finalize the preparation of the microfluidic channel. The plasma treatment led to wettability alteration of the glass and PDMS surfaces to a hydrophilic state. 1.5 mm PTFE tubing was employed to facilitate the introduction of inlet materials into the channel. The tubing was integrated into a microfluidic flow control system (OB1 MK3+ flow controller, ElveFlow, Paris, France).

4.9. Fabrication of Microchannels on PDMS

Due to the constraints associated with conducting z-stack experiments to examine the positioning of nanoparticles at the 5CB–aqueous phase interface within the microchannels, even the use of a 40x objective lens proved insufficient. Consequently, it became essential to fabricate the microchannel on a PDMS substrate. This technique facilitated the bonding of the microchannel to a coverslip, thereby enabling the application of a 63x objective lens, which significantly enhanced observation capabilities. The sequential process involved in fabricating a microchannel on PDMS is shown in Figure 9(g-j). For this purpose, a pre-fabricated etched microchannel on a glass slide was selected and subjected to sonication in a 1% vol DMOAP aqueous solution for 15 min. Following this, it was rinsed with water, absolute ethanol and 2-propanol, and then dried with nitrogen. A mold was prepared using the DMOAP-coated microchannel on the glass slide, covered with aluminum foil. A transparent PDMS mixture was cast onto the mold and cured for 2 h at 60 °C in an oven. After allowing the mold to cool to ambient temperature, the PDMS incorporating the printed protrusions of the microchannel on the glass slide was carefully excised and subsequently treated with OTS within a vacuum chamber for 30 min. The OTS-coated PDMS piece was then placed in a flat mold made from a fresh glass slide and aluminum foil. A transparent PDMS mixture was poured onto the prepared mold and heated for 2 hours at 60 °C in an oven. Finally, upon reaching room temperature, the upper layer of PDMS where the microchannel cavities were formed was gently peeled from the PDMS substrate featuring the channel protrusions. The cavities of the microchannel fabricated on the PDMS exhibit symmetry with the cavities of the microchannel on the glass slide. Following the previously described methodology, the PDMS was precisely perforated to create the inlet and outlet ports and then bonded to a coverslip using oxygen plasma treatment.

Figure 9. Essential steps illustrating the fabrication of microfluidic platforms. (a) DMOAP coating on a glass slide. (b) The coating of positive photoresist and maskless photolithography. (c) Photoresist developing. (d) The creation of channel cavities through wet etching using a 7:1 BOE. (e) Configuration of the patterned glass slide after the photoresist stripping. (f) Preparation of the glass-PDMS microfluidic channel following the bonding process facilitated by oxygen plasma treatment. Images (g–j) represent the sequential process involved in fabricating a microchannel on PDMS, utilizing a pre-fabricated microchannel on a glass slide, as established in step (e). (g) Creation of the corresponding microchannel protrusions on PDMS. (h) Detaching the PDMS piece with the microchannel cavities from the PDMS substrate that contains the protrusions. (i) Configuration of the microchannel on PDMS. (j) The coverslip-PDMS microfluidic channel is prepared after bonding via oxygen plasma treatment.

4.10. Functionalization of the Microchannels

To enable contact between the aqueous phase and 5CB flow, the surface wetting of half the channel was modified via DMOAP functionalization to retain hydrophobicity. For this end, water flow was initially introduced to the microfluidic channel platform for at least 15 min. 1 vol % DMOAP aqueous solution was then fed to the channel from the opposite inlet. The optimal inlet pressures of water and DMOAP solution, which effectively established a stable virtual walled flow system, were regulated at 150 and 140 mbar, respectively. The functionalizing process was carried out for 30 min. Afterward, the tubing supplying DMOAP was gently detached, and the entire channel was thoroughly rinsed with water for at least 15 min. Next, a flow of 5CB was introduced to the channel while maintaining water flow at a reduced pressure of 10 mbar. This approach was implemented to mitigate the risk of contamination or loss of hydrophobicity, as the water flow was deliberately continued without interruption. As 5CB progressed along a specified pathway within the channel,

a soft interface was established between the 5CB and water.^{40, 41} All microfluidic flow experiments were performed at room temperature.

4.11. Microscopy of Microfluidic Channel Systems

Micrographs in microfluidic experiments were captured using a Zeiss LSM 900 Fluorescence Confocal Polarizing Microscope (Jena, Germany), which features a rotatable polarizer and analyzer set at 45°–135° in the experiments. The FCPM technique was employed to ascertain the alignment of LC mesogens within the channel by acquiring confocal images at 0° and 90° polarization of the fluorescence excitation light, thereby elucidating the 3D structure. For this imaging process, the fluorescent Nile Red dye ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 549 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 628 \text{ nm}$) was used at a concentration of 0.01 wt % in 5CB.⁷⁵ The *z*-stack experiments for Nile Red were performed by a 63x objective with a 5% intensity of 651 nm laser, a 53 μm pinhole, and an 800 V master gain. Further, the positioning of the nanoparticles along the channel was determined by FCM imaging. This was achieved by tracking the FITC dye molecules ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 490 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 515 \text{ nm}$), which are located at the core of the synthesized core-shell F-SiNPs. The *z*-stack parameters for FITC were configured to a 4.5% intensity of 488 nm laser, a 53 μm pinhole, and an 800 V master gain, using a 63x objective lens.

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Author Contributions

P. E. conducted experiments and characterizations. E. B. supervised the research. Both authors contributed to data interpretation, discussions, and manuscript preparation.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

Data Availability Statement

All raw experimental data supporting the findings of this study are openly available on zenodo.org.

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